

The Collection of Sources and Secondary Literature on Islamic law and Jurisprudence by the Center for Electronic Databases on Islamic Jurisprudence, Irān

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In 1422/2001, the Center for Electronic Databases on Islamic Jurisprudence (*Markaz al-mu'jam al-fiqhī*), based at the University of Qom, Iran (www.almarkaz.net), released the third version of *al-Mu'jam al-fiqhī* (Al-Mojam, 2 CDs; www.almarkaz.net/almojam.htm), which is a collection of sources and secondary literature on Islamic law and jurisprudence (*fiqh*), primarily in Arabic but also in Persian. 1,131 works were included in this edition of Al-Mojam, amounting to, in aggregate, over 3,000 volumes or individual books.

Structure and content of Al-Mojam (*al-Mu'jam*)

The principle governing the selection of works is not specified in the program. The collection as a whole is divided into 26 rubrics or sections ("collections of books," *majmū'āt al-kutub*), organized mainly according to their genre or theological and jurisprudential subject-matter. The numbering of the works is continuous and consecutive. Within each section, individual works are arranged in chronological order, according to the dates of death of their authors, from the earliest until the most recent—this being the organizing principle of the bio-bibliographical genre traditionally favored for materials of this kind. Indications are also given of an individual work's number within the series as a whole, the name of its author, its title, and the number of volumes it takes up.

*Summary of the sections or "collections of books" (majmū'āt al-kutub). These are as follows. 1) Shī'ī fiqh (jurisprudence) from the beginning until the 8th/14th century. 2) Shī'ī fiqh after the 8th/14th century. 3) Shī'ī fiqh: advisory briefs or *responsa* (*fatāwā*) and epistles on practical*

matters (*rasā'il 'amaliyya*) issued by Shī'ī authorities. 4) Fiqh of the Zaydī school. 5) Fiqh of the Shāfi'ī madhhab. 6) Fiqh of the Mālikī madhhab. 7) Fiqh of the Ḥanafī madhhab. 8) Fiqh of the Ḥanbalī madhhab. 9) Fiqh of the Zāhirī school. 10) Independent juridical sources. 11) Sources on jurisprudential terminology. 12) Shī'ī sources on *ḥadīth*: section on fiqh. 13) Shī'ī sources on *ḥadīth*: general section. 14) Sunnī sources on *ḥadīth*: section on fiqh. 15) Sunnī sources on *ḥadīth*: general section. 16) Shī'ī sources on Qur'ānic exegesis (*tafsīr*). 17) Sunnī sources on Qur'ānic exegesis (*tafsīr*). 18) Foundations or principles of jurisprudence (*uṣūl al-fiqh*) according to the Shī'īs. 19) Foundations or principles of jurisprudence (*uṣūl al-fiqh*) according to the Sunnīs. 20) Major sources on the transmitters of *ḥadīth* (*rijāl al-ḥadīth*) among the Shī'īs. 21) Major sources on the transmitters of *ḥadīth* (*rijāl*) among the Sunnīs. 22) Reference works in Arabic. 23) Genealogies (*ansāb*) and various dictionaries (*ma'ājim*). 24) Historical chronicles (*maṣādir al-ta'rīkh*). 25) Lives of the Prophet and the Imams. 26) Sources on the Arabic language: lexicographical works, Arabic-language dictionaries.

The first section contains 40 works, the earliest of which is the *Fiqh al-Riḍā* of 'Alī b. Bābūyah (d. 329/940-41). Among the authors of works included in this section are acknowledged authorities of Shī'ī Islam such as al-Shaykh al-Mufīd (d. 413/1022), twelve of whose works are included; al-Shaykh al-Ṭūsī (d. 460/1067), six works; and others. The last in chronological order within this “collection” is the two-volume *Kashf al-rumūz* by al-Fāḍil al-Ābī (d. 690/1291).

The number of works in the second section or “collection” amounts to 173, more than four times that of the first. A considerable number of these date from the 13th and 14th centuries of the Hijra (18th and 19th centuries CE), while over twenty are by contemporary authors. The earliest work in this section is the *Jam' al-khilāf wal-withāq* of 'Alī b. Muḥammad al-Qummī (8th/14th century). The great Imami theologian and jurist al-'Allāma al-Ḥillī (d. 726/1326) is broadly represented with eleven works, in particular his nine-volume *Mukhtalif al-ḥadīth* and ten-volume *Tadhkirat al-fuqahā'*. The last entries in this section (arranged by author's date of death) are nine works by al-Sayyid al-Gulpāyagānī (d. 1414/1993).

In the third section, 62 works are collected (a number of them in Persian) by later authors, 35 of them contemporary. The first of these is the *Jāmi' al-shatāt* (in Persian) by al-

Mirzī al-Qummī (d. 1231/1816). The last (again, reckoning by the author’s date of death) is the seven-volume *Kalimat al-taqwā* by al-Shaykh Muḥammad Amīn Zayn al-Dīn (d. 1419/1998).

The fiqh of the various non-Shīʿī schools and *madhhabs* is represented in markedly smaller quantities than is the fiqh of the Shīʿīs themselves: four works of the Zaydīs, thirteen of the Shāfiʿīs, nine of the Mālikīs, eight of the Ḥanafīs, three of the Ḥanbalīs, and one of the Zāhirīs. At the same time, however, the sections on these schools contain major works, for the most part multi-volume sets, attributed to the major authorities of these schools. For the Shāfiʿīs these include the eight-volume *Kitāb al-umm* of the Imām al-Shāfiʿī (d. 204/820), the 20-volume *al-Majmūʿ* and the eight-volume *Rawḍat al-ṭālibīn* of Muḥyī l-Dīn al-Nawawī (d. 676/1277), and others. For the Mālikīs we find the two-volume *al-Muwattaʿa* of the Imam Mālik b. Anas (d. 179/795), and others. Ḥanafī contributions include the 30-volume *al-Mabsūṭ* by al-Sarakhsī (d. 483/1090), the seven-volume *Badāʿiʿ al-ṣanāʿiʿ* by Abū Bakr al-Kashānī (d. 587/1191), and others. Ḥanbalī contributions include the twelve-volume *al-Mughnī* of Ibn Qudāma (d. 620/1223). For the Zāhirīs, we have the eleven-volume *al-Muḥallā* of Ibn Ḥazm (d. 456/1064).

Next comes the section on “independent juridical sources,” linking to the two-volume *Bidāyat al-mujtahid wa-nihāyat al-muqtaṣid* of Ibn Rushd (d. 595/1199), and the four-volume *Subul al-salām* of Ibn Ḥajar al-ʿAsqalānī (d. 852/1449). Half of the eight entries in this section pertain to contemporary authors.

Section 11 consists of fourteen works devoted to juridical terminology, nine of them written by contemporary authors. The earliest entry in this section is the two-volume *al-Qawāʿid wal-fawāʿid* by the authoritative Shīʿī theologian and jurist al-Shahīd al-Awwal (Muḥammad al-ʿĀmilī, d. 786/1384).

Section 12, on Shīʿī traditions as sources of *fiqh*, represents a total of 39 works attributed to the Shīʿī Imams, beginning with the four-volume *Nahj al-balāgha* (sermons and aphorisms of ʿAlī). This section also includes early Shīʿī authors (mainly 3rd/9th – 5th/11th centuries) who had leading roles in the building of the Imami school (Jaʿfarī madhhab). Among these are the two-volume *al-Maḥāsīn* of Aḥmad al-Barqī (d. 274/887 or 280/893); the *Baṣāʿir al-darajāt* of Muḥammad b. al-Ḥasan al-Ṣaffār (d. 290/903); and the eight-volume *al-Kāfi fi ʿulūm al-fiqh* of al-Kulīnī (d. 329/941), founder of the Imāmī school of jurisprudence in Iran. This last-named work (*al-Kāfi*) is recognized as the most authoritative collection of Shīʿī traditions (16

thousand ḥadīths) and the first of the “four sources” (*al-uṣūl al-arbaʿa*) or “four books” (*al-kutub al-arbaʿa*) of the Imāmī school. Among the eleven works included in this section by the Imami *faqīh* Ibn Bābūyah al-Ṣadūq al-Qummī (d. 381/991) is the four-volume collection of Shīʿī traditions (9000), *Man lā yaḥḍuruḥu al-faqīh*, recognized as the second of the Imami “four sources.” Also included in this section are two works by the renowned al-Shaykh al-Ṭūsī (d. 460/1067), *Tahdhīb al-aḥkām* (13,000 ḥadīths) and *al-Mabsūṭ* (5500), respectively the third and fourth “sources” of Imami fiqh.

Section 13 is one of the largest according to the number of works it contains, which is 183 (31 of these by contemporary authors). Like the previous section, it contains sources on Shīʿī traditions, but here in the broader context of the Shīʿī religious sciences, in addition to or aside from fiqh. These are theology and dogma, the Imamate, the history of the Shīʿīs, the merits of the Imams, and so forth. One of the last of the works in this section (according to the date of the authors’ death) is the ten-volume *Mustadrak safīnat al-biḥār* by Shaykh ʿAlī al-Namāzī (d. 1405/1984).

Just as these two preceding sections were devoted to the Shīʿīs, the thirteenth and fourteenth “collections” include Sunnī sources on ḥadīth, in conformity with Sunnī fiqh and the Sunnī religious sciences more broadly. The earliest Sunnī works in the fourteenth “collection” (of which there are 22 in all) are the *Ikhtilāf al-ḥadīth* and *Musnad* of the Imām al-Shāfiʿī (d. 204/820), who has already been mentioned. Here too are represented all the major Sunnī “canonical” collections of ḥadīth: the two-volume *al-Sunan* by al-Dārimī (d. 255/869), the two eight-volume works entitled *al-Ṣaḥīḥ* by al-Bukhārī (d. 256/869) and Muslim (d. 261/875), the five-volume *al-Sunan* of al-Tirmidhī (d. 279/892), and others.

The fifteenth section comprises the largest “collection” in the database (204 titles, of which only 22 are by contemporary authors), consisting of works in various genres. A considerable portion of these date from between the 2nd/8th and the 5th/11th centuries. By far the earliest of these are the *al-Farāʾid* ascribed to Sufyān al-Thawrī (d. 161/778), the *Musnad* of ʿAbd Allāh b. al-Mubārak (d. 181/797), the *Musnad* of Sulaymān b. Dāʿūd (d. 204/820), and others.

The next two sections (16 and 17) are devoted to sources on exegesis, or interpretation of the Qurʾān (*tafsīr*), associated with the Shīʿīs and the Sunnīs (28 works for each respectively).

The earliest Shīʿī Qurʾānic commentary is the *Tafsīr* of Abū Ḥamza al-Thumālī (d. 148/765 or 150/767); the latest (aside from seven works by contemporary authors included here) is the twenty-volume *al-Mīzān fī tafsīr al-Qurʾān* by one of the most authoritative modern Iranian scholars, Sayyid Muḥammad-Ḥusayn al-Ṭabāṭabāʾī (d. 1402/1981). In this same section is the ten-volume commentary *al-Tibyān fī tafsīr al-Qurʾān* by al-Shaykh al-Ṭūsī (d. 460/1067), as well as the ten-volume *Tafsīr majmaʿ al-bayān* of al-Ṭabarsī (d. 548/1153).

The earliest Sunnī works of Qurʾānic exegesis are the two-volume *Tafsīr al-Qurʾān* of Mujāhid b. Jabr al-Makkī (d. 104/722), the *al-Nāsikh wal-mansūkh* of al-Sadūsī (d. 117/735), and the *Tafsīr al-Qurʾān* attributed to Sufyān al-Thawrī (d. 161/778). Among the latest are the six-volume *al-Durr al-manṣūr* of Jalāl al-Dīn al-Suyūṭī (d. 911/1505), while the last work in this section (aside from three works by contemporary authors) is the *Faḥḥ al-qadīr* of al-Shawqānī (d. 1255/1839).

In the following two sections (18 and 19) works on “the foundations of jurisprudence” (*uṣūl al-fiqh*) are represented, as these pertain to the Shīʿīs (39 works, nine of them contemporary) and to the Sunnīs (eight works in all). Earliest among the Shīʿī entries is *al-Tadhkira bi-uṣūl al-fiqh* by al-Shaykh al-Mufīd (d. 413/1022), the latest (according to date of author’s death) is the two-volume *Ifādat al-ʿawāʾid* of al-Sayyid al-Gulpāygānī (d. 1414/1993). Among the Sunnī works in this genre are the eight-volume *al-Aḥkām* by the Zāhirī Ibn Ḥazm (d. 456/1064), the six-volume *al-Maḥṣūl* of al-Rāzī (d. 606/1209), and last in chronological order, the four-volume *al-Aḥkām* of al-Āmidī (d. 631/1234).

Sections 20 and 21 present major sources on the transmitters of traditions (*rijāl al-ḥadīth*) pertaining to the Shīʿīs (39 works, of which nine are contemporary) and to the Sunnīs (56 works, only one of them contemporary). The earliest of the Shīʿī works included here is the *Taʾrīkh āl Zurāra* of Abū Ghālib al-Zurārī (d. 368/979, GAS 1:544). This section also includes well-known Shīʿī bibliographical reference books, such as al-Najāshī’s (d. 450/1055) *al-Rijāl*, and al-Ṭūsī’s (d. 460/1067) *al-Rijāl*, *al-Fihrist*, and *Ikhtiyār maʾrifat al-rijāl* (the latter in two volumes), as well as others. The last work in the sequence is the 24-volume *Muʾjam rijāl al-ḥadīth* of al-Khawāʾī (al-Khūʾī?) (d. 1411/1990).

Among the Sunnīs, the earliest work in this genre is the three-volume *Kitāb al-siyar al-kabīr*, composed by Muḥammad al-Shaybānī (d. 189/805), a founding figure of Islamic law. Here

are also to be found the eight-volume *al-Ṭabaqāt al-kubrā* of Ibn Sa‘d (d. 230/845); works of al-Bukhārī (d. 255/870), including his nine-volume *al-Ta’rīkh al-kabīr*; six works of al-Dhahabī (d. 748/1347), including the 23-volume *Siyar a‘lām al-nubalā’*; six works of Ibn Ḥajar (d. 852/1448), including his twelve-volume *Tahdhīb al-tahdhīb* and seven-volume *Lisān al-mīzān*; and others.

The 22nd section, Arabic bibliographical reference works, comprises fifteen works (five of them contemporary), which are not subdivided into Shī‘ī and Sunnī groupings. Among these are the *Fihrist* of Ibn al-Nadīm (d. 385/995 or 388/998), the two-volume *Kashf al-zunūn* of Ḥājji Khalīfa (d. 1067/1656), the 26-volume *al-Dharī‘a ilā taṣānīf al-Shī‘a* by the Imāmī Shī‘ī Āghā Bozorg al-Tehrānī (d. 1389/1969), the eight-volume *al-A‘lām* by al-Ziriklī (d. 1410/1989), and the thirteen-volume *Mu‘jam al-mu‘allifīn* by ‘Umar Kaḥḥāla (d.????).

The 23rd section, which is not large (seven works in all), includes sources on genealogy (*ansāb*), provides notable examples of this genre, beginning with the *Ansāb al-ashrāf* of al-Balādhurī (d. 279/892), and ending with the *Mu‘jam qabā’il al-‘Arab* by ‘Umar Kaḥḥāla (see previous paragraph).

The following section (24) comprises 24 works (four of them by contemporary authors) in the genre of historical chronicles (*al-ta’rīkh*). These include the three-volume *Futūḥ al-buldān* of the already-mentioned al-Balādhurī, the two-volume *Ta’rīkh* of al-Ya‘qūbī (d. 284/897), the eight-volume *Ta’rīkh* of al-Ṭabarī (d. 310/922), *al-Tanbīh wal-ishrāf* and *Akḥbār al-zamān* (or *Murūj al-dhahab*) by al-Mas‘ūdī (d. 345/956), and the fourteen-volume *al-Bidāya wal-nihāya* of Ibn Kathīr (d. 774/1372). The *Faḍā’il Makka* ascribed to al-Ḥasan al-Baṣrī (d. 110/729, GAS 341, 592-93) is the earliest of all these, while the latest is the seven-volume *Ta’rīkh* (or *Kitāb al-‘ibar*) of Ibn Khaldūn (d. 808/1405).

The 25th section contains works by both Shī‘ī and Sunnī authors, in the genre of “lives” of the Prophets and Imams. Here there are 84 works (32 of them contemporary). The earliest of these are the *Maqatal* *al-Ḥusayn* (GAS 1:308) of Abū Mikhnaf (d. 157/774), the *Waq‘at Ṣiffīn* of al-Minqarī (d. 212/827), the four-volume *Sīra*, or *Life of the Prophet* by Ibn Hishām (d. 218/833). This section includes many works by well-known authors, devoted to “the stories of the prophets” (*qīṣaṣ al-anbiyā’*), the “infallibility” and “merits” of the Prophets and Imams, and the biographies of the Imams.

The 26th and final section includes sources (*maṣādir*) with the character of reference and auxiliary works (twenty of them in all). These are dictionaries by medieval Arabic authors, beginning with the eight-volume *Kitāb al-‘ayn* by the renowned lexicographer and grammarian al-Khalīl (d. 170/786), and ending with the *Muhktaṣar al-ma‘ānī* of Sa‘d al-Dīn al-Taftazānī (d. 792/1390). Among the works included in this section are well-known language dictionaries: the fifteen-volume *Lisān al-‘Arab* of Ibn Manẓūr (d. 711/1311) and the ten-volume *Tāj al-‘arūs* by al-Zabīdī (d. 1205/1791).

The structure and content of the Al-Mojam database allow us to classify the material it contains in two ways, broadly speaking. The first of these is according to the characteristics of the subject-matter and genres of the works it contains; the second is according to the association of these works with one or the other of the branches of Islam.

As for the first way, we find, first of all, a clearly-delineated grouping of entries devoted entirely to Islamic law and jurisprudence (*fiqh*). These are sections 1-11, 18 and 19, in which 382 works on *fiqh* are represented, in addition to 39 Shī‘ī works (in section 12) and 22 Sunnī works (in section 14) which are presented to the faithful of each sect (respectively) as sources of *fiqh*. Then we find a second grouping which comprises works written in various genres, representing disciplines that are necessary for the study of *fiqh*, namely: the science of ḥadīth (*‘ilm al-ḥadīth*), the transmitters of ḥadīth (*rijāl al-ḥadīth*), and Qur’ānic exegesis (*‘ilm al-tafsīr*). These are sections 12-17 and 20-21, in which 599 works are represented. Finally, there is a third grouping which consists of bibliographical reference works, works of genealogy, chronicles, “lives,” and Arabic-language dictionaries, which (in the context of this database) fulfill the function of, figuratively speaking, “serving” *fiqh* and the other religious disciplines. These are sections 22-26, in which 150 works are represented.

As for the characteristics of the works with regard to their association with one or the other of the fixed trends within Islam, here again it is possible to divide the whole into three groups, as follows. (1) Sections in which only works by Shī‘ī authors are collected (sections 1-4, 12-13, 16, 18, 20), totalling 417. (2) Sections which include only works by Sunnīs (sections 5-9, 14-15, 17, 19, 21), totalling 534. (3) Sections in which the works are not divided into Shī‘ī and Sunnī (sections 10-11, 22-26), totalling 180.

The number of works devoted to Shīī fiqh clearly prevails over that devoted to the fiqh of the Sunnīs. At the same time, however, Sunnī works in other disciplines (sections 15, 21) outnumber their Shīī counterparts. On the one hand, the ratio of Sunnī to Shīī works in Al-Mojam (534 to 417) reflects the actual quantitative superiority that the Sunnī literary heritage enjoys over its Shīī counterpart. But on the other hand, this preponderance of Sunnī entries in Al-Mojam speaks to the credit of its developers, who have provided researchers on Islam with an extraordinarily broad and diverse body of material.

System requirements and program installation

The developers of the program state that it was adapted to Windows 95/98/2000 (any language). The reviewers for this article have worked in Windows XP, and have found a noteworthy absence of errors in the program, apart from several instances of incorrect representation of Arabic symbols in the menu. A special key must be supplied: this key is attached to the LPT portal while the computer is switched off; then, when the computer is switched on, the key is left in until the beginning of installation. This key provides a defense against unlicensed copying.

Upon installation it is possible to choose among the following options. (1) For the language of interface, there is a choice of English, Arabic or Persian. For the latter two it is necessary to have a localized operating system or, when working in Windows XP, to have installed an Arabic/Persian code page for non-Unicode programs. (2) Regarding installation, two options are available: a) full, requiring around 1600 MB of disk space, with the installation disk no longer required after installation; and b) incomplete (CD-ROM), requiring around 870 MB. The program is provided with sufficiently detailed information. However, the English translation is not always accurate and its menu commands can lead to confusion, especially at the beginning.

The program's basic capabilities

Illustration 1 shows the main window of the Al-Mojam program, with the open window *Books List*. For the sake of convenience, the most commonly-used functions are performed by a series of separate icons situated on the two toolbars of the program's main window. These toolbars are arranged in *horizontal* (A) and *vertical* (B) rows.

Pic. M1 - Book List

The horizontal toolbar presents four groups of icons (moving from left to right, without enumeration). These are:

A.1 Operations with books.

A.2 Search operations.

A.3 Reading options.

A.4 The help function.

The vertical toolbar has icons that perform auxiliary functions.

The horizontal toolbar. The A.1 group consists of icons that control operations with books, as follows. 1) Opening the *Books List* window (detailed description in the following paragraph). 2) Closing a current book. 3) Proceeding to the next book. 4) Closing all. 5) Closing other open books. 6) Proceeding to a particular page. 7) Opening a table of contents. 8) Opening a screen with bibliographical data on particular sources.

The *Books List* window presents a list of all the works included in the database. These are arranged into sections (see Pic. M1 above), within which they are further arranged according to chronological order (according to date of author's death). Numbering is continuous, with each volume assigned a number in the series.¹ Much of this window is taken up by basic information regarding the works. At the top of the window we find: 1) the number assigned to each volume in the database; 2) the title of the book (abbreviated); 3) the author's name (short version); 4) the number of volumes, if the work takes up more than one volume. The information provided in each of these fields may be arranged in ascending or descending order.

Then, just above the bottom of the window, come tools for navigating the book list, as follows. 5) The quick search field: when the user types a book title or author's name into this field, this information is automatically highlighted. Then, by shifting the cursor up and down, the user can arrive at the results of the search. 6) This field allows the user to select a juridical topic (such as *al-ṣalāt*), if such a heading exists in the database. 7) This field allows the user to select one of the database library's 26 sections (see above). The first work within the section that has just been selected will then be automatically highlighted.

Finally, at the bottom of the window, come the following icons: 8) *Cancel*, or closing the *Books List*; 9) *Section*, switching over to a selected juridical section or heading; 10) *Content*, providing a table of contents for a selected volume; 11) *Print*, printing an entire bibliographical list or table²; 12) the *Help* function; 13) *Reading*, moving to the beginning of a selected work.

A work is presented in its entirety if it consists of a single volume, or according to volume if it consists of more than one volume. At the very beginning of each book there is a presentation of the publication data of the original edition. The text is reproduced very carefully. The original pagination is preserved. The pages are separated by a solid red line, with the page number appearing in parentheses at the beginning of each page. Furthermore, to all appearances, the layout of the original, published edition is preserved line by line. 3) Additional material such as notes and scholarly apparatus is kept at the bottom of the page,

¹ This procedure seems inconvenient, because it might have been easier for the user if entries had been numbered according to complete works, rather than individual volumes. (translator)

² For the results of this kind of printing (PDF file), see the [Russian] site "Islamovedennie v SPbF IV RAN" (www.orientalstudies.ru/almojam.pdf)

beginning with the word *hāmish* (margin) in parentheses. A green dotted line separates this material from the text itself.

Group A.2 of the *horizontal toolbar* presents icons for the search function, as follows. 1) Search window (see below). 2) View search results. 3) Range of sources for conducting a search. 4) Saving search results. 5-6) Going to the previous or next occurrence of the selected item. 7-8) Going to the selected item within the previous or next book in the database. 9) Stopping a search. 10) Turning the highlighting of the searched word on or off.

Group A.3 presents icons that organize the “reading options,” or interface. These provide ways for arranging open windows, including the simultaneous showing of several windows, which is convenient for managing various passages or fragments of text at the same time; changing fonts; and choice of background image. Group A.4 provides icons that provide help with the program.

The vertical toolbar. This presents icons that provide access to auxiliary functions and materials (the windows described in what follows are similar, in many respects, to the *Books List* window). 1) *Feqhi Sections*. On the right side of this window is a list of 53 juridical headings or “sections.” When the user selects one of these, a list appears on the left side of the window giving the titles of works that deal with this topic. The *Reading* icon then opens the work at the place in which the selected topic is located. 2) *Subjects*. This allows the user to create a subject index, or system of bookmarks. 3) *Authors*. This provides brief information on the database’s 415 authors, arranged in alphabetical order and supplied fairly often with references to sources and modern literature. The available options include: (a) the *Search* icon, providing a search throughout the entire database (see below); (b) a search **by** author’s name (a quick search field, no. 5 on Illustration 1); and (c) **a help search** (see above). 4) *Narrators*: here we have brief information on the 15,468 transmitters who appear in the database. The same options are available here as for the authors. 5) *Terms*: a reference list of 3,083 terms in Arabic, and very briefly in English. The same options are available here as for the authors and narrators. 5) *Sihah al-Jawhariy*: an Arabic-language dictionary, offering the same options as the previous. 6-7) *Previous/Next part*: going on to the previous or next part. 8) *Print block*: printing a highlighted block of text.

Pic. M2 - Search

The *Search* window (see Pic. M2) is divided into four blocks. In the *Statements* block, the user can enter the word or phrase that he/she wishes to search for. Under *Extraction* come several icons, which allow the user to add variants of the words already entered in the *Statements* block; these variants are apparently taken from the vocabulary that is compiled in the *Main Statement* window. These icons are as follows. 1) *Derivatives*. These are all the derived forms of a word (for example, forms of a word derived from a root that has been entered). 2) *Similar* words (for example, variants of a word with different spellings, as we find in final *yā'* with and without dots). 3) *With suffixes*, variants with all suffixes. 4) *With affixes*, all words in which the word that is being searched for appears only in part. 5) *With prefixes*, with connected prepositions etc. 6) *Dictionary*. This enables the user to open a list of indexed words, out of which the user can then select the word he/she is looking for.

So for example, if a user needs to locate “Ibn al-Jawzī,” the *Similar* icon adds to the field *Main Statement* all the variant spellings of that name that may be encountered in the texts, that is, with all the different ways of writing *alif* (including such unlikely possibilities as *alif* with

mādda), and all the different ways of writing final *yā'*. *With prefixes* adds variants with connected prepositions. The developers of Al-Mojam decided to take into account the possibility of misprints, thereby increasing the accuracy of a search, to a noteworthy extent.

In the bottom two rows are icons with the following functions. *Delete*, i.e., deleting a word entered in the *Main statement* window. *Del[ete] all*; *Range*, the selection of works in which a search is to be performed. It is possible to select works either individually, or according to their juridical topics, or according to their section within the database library. A numerical value is provided for the number of words allowed between the words in the *Statements* field. *Cancel* provides for exiting from the search function. Then come *Help*; *Search*, initiating a new search; and *Volumes*, the number of volumes among which a search is to be performed.

The window *Search Results* has the following appearance (Illustration 3). The upper block indicates general points of reference: the number of a volume within the database as a whole, the work's title, the author's name, and the number of the volume within the work as a

whole (if applicable). The lower block indicates detailed points of reference regarding the work selected in the upper block, namely, the variant of the selected word and the page number.

It is possible to carry out the following operations with the results of a search.

1) *Reading*: this yields open pages of a text, in which the search results are highlighted. Within the search results, it is possible to move back and forth with the help of the icons in block A.2 (see above). 2) *Print*: there are two different ways of printing the results of a search: in part, giving only the points of reference of the search results; and full printing, together with brief citations. 3) *File*: this is a collection of results in text file (*.txt), also in two different variants.

The developers of Al-Mojam have thought this search system through with tremendous care, just as they have done with the options for working with the search results. Moreover, despite the remarkable size of this textual database, searches in it proceed with considerably more speed than they do in other databases that are much smaller in volume. The program saves the results of a user's work: whenever the program is reopened, it takes off from the same place as when it was last closed. The results of the previous search can be obtained at A.2.2 (see above).

The materials represented in Al-Mojam, the program's intelligible interface, and its convenient search system all contribute considerably toward broadening the possibilities available to researchers in Islamic studies, and will help them to make sound, effective decisions as they face their tasks—tasks which include the preparation of critical editions of Arabic texts, filling lacunae in manuscripts, and seeking and identifying terms, prosopographical and toponymical data, and so forth.